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D2.1 Dataset description

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List of acronyms

CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CryoSat-2	Satellite mission
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DSLMM	Deviation from Sea Level Mean
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Network
Envisat	Satellite mission
ERA-Interim	Global atmospheric reanalysis
ERS-2	Satellite mission
EVRF2007	European Vertical Reference Frame 2007
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute
GPS	Global Positioning System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
Jason 1, 2, 3	Satellite missions
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SARAL/AltiKa	Satellite mission
Sentinel 3A/B	Satellite missions
SGDR	Sensor and Geophysical Data Record
SMHI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
SSH	Sea Surface Height
TG	Tide Gauge
TOPEX/Poseidon	Satellite mission
TUM	Technical University of Munich
WP2, WP3.7, WP4.2	Work Package 2, 3.7 and 4.2

General introduction

Baltic+ SEAL aims at providing an improved and consistent description of the sea level variability in the Baltic Sea and Danish Straits in terms of seasonal and inter-annual variation, by combining satellite observations with tide gauge and ocean model data. Additionally, an experimental higher temporal-resolution (2-3 days) gridded product is investigated, aimed at improving the preconditioning of storm surge forecasts. These products include data sets from satellite altimetry observations, tide gauge data, GPS data, ocean model data and SAR and optical data.

The purpose of deliverable D2.1 in WP2 is to collect and describe these data sets for internal use. The final product will be described in the user manual of the project.

Altimetry data (TUM)

Abstract

Satellite altimetry observations are used to measure the height of the sea surface. The Sea Surface Height (SSH) is the difference between the orbital height of an altimetry satellite above a reference ellipsoid (e.g. TOPEX ellipsoid) and the range between the satellite's centre of mass and the sea surface. The distance between satellite and sea surface is computed by measuring the travel time of a radar pulse emitted by the altimeter to the surface. In order to estimate reliable sea surface elevation, various geophysical corrections have to be applied (e.g. tropospheric delay, ocean tides etc.).

The description of the altimetry data contains information about the source data applied in the Algorithm Development to reprocess the altimetric waveforms and the auxiliary data adopted to correct the estimated Ranges in order to derive the Sea Surface Heights.

Meta-data

Figure 1 shows the used satellite altimetry missions. The investigation time period is from 1995-05 until 2019-05.

Figure 1 Temporal availability of all satellite altimetry missions. Considered missions are highlighted in green.

The spatial coverage is limited to the key area of the Baltic Sea $9^{\circ}E/31^{\circ}E$ and $53^{\circ}N/66^{\circ}N$. Altimetry observations are provided as along-track instantaneous snapshots of the sea surface height. All used altimetry missions are located on repeat orbit configurations, which means fixed revisit times of each satellite mission. Table 1 lists all revisit times of the missions.

Table 1: Repeat times of the altimeter missions

Mission (agency)	ERS-2 (ESA)	TOPEX/Poseidon (CNES/NASA)	Jason-1,2,3 (CNES/NASA)	Envisat (ESA)	SARAL/AltiKa (CNES/ISRO)	CryoSat-2 (ESA)	Sentinel-3A/B (ESA/Copernicus)
Revisit Time (days)	35	9.9	9.9	35	35	369	27

Depending on the mission the range observations are available in a 10Hz (TOPEX/Poseidon), 20Hz (Jason-1,2,3, ERS-2, Envisat, Cryosat-2, Sentinel-3A/B) or 40Hz (SARAL/AltiKa) sampling rate. All geophysical corrections and additional datasets (e.g. distance to coast) are provided at the same time and spatial sampling rate.

The altimetry waveform data, required for the range estimation, and some of the geophysical corrections are provided by the official Sensor and Geophysical Data Record (SGDR) or similar products of the agencies. Following description summarizes all necessary altimeter data, enabling the calculation of SSH. Auxiliary datasets, not necessarily required for SSH estimation, are treated separately.

Data description

Following table lists all applied altimeter data and required geophysical corrections for SSH computation. Extended mission phases (e.g. geodetic phase) are labelled by their nominal mission period.

Table 2: Altimeter data and corrections for Sea Surface Height computation

Corrections/ Altimeter data	Altimeter Missions								
	TOPEX/ Poseidon	Jason- 1	Jason- 2	Jason- 3	ERS-2	Envisat	SARAL/AltiKa	CryoSat-2	Sentinel- 3A/B
Orbit	ALTSDR-L1B	SGDR-E	SGDR-D	SGDR-T	GFZ VER13 SLCCI [1]	SGDR-E	SGDR-D	SGDR-T	SGDR Reaper v01.08
Waveforms	-	SGDR-E	SGDR-D	SGDR-T	SGDR Reaper v01.08	SGDR v3.1	SGDR-T	SIR_SAR_L1B Baseline C	NT-SGDR CODA
Wet troposphere	GPD/GPD ¹ [2] [3]			VMF3 ² [4]	GPD/GPD ¹ [2] [3]		VMF3 ² [4]	VMF3 ² [4]	VMF3 ² [4]
Dry troposphere	VMF3 ² [4]								
Ionosphere	NOAA Ionosphere Climatology (NIC09) [5]								
Sea State Bias	ALTSDR-L1B	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6]	ALES+ [6] / SAMOSA2 [7] NT-SGDR CODA
Ocean Tide	FES2014 [8]								
Loading Tide	FES2014 [8]								
Atmospheric pressure	Inverse barometric pressure (ECMWF) + Dynamic Atmosphere correction (MOG2D)HF [9]								
Solid Earth Tide	ALTSDR-L1B	SGDR-E	SGDR-D	SGDR-T	SGDR Reaper v01.08	SGDR v3.1	SGDR-T	IERS Conventions 2010 [10]	IERS Conventions 2010 [10]

¹ GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite Systems) derived Path Delay Plus (GPD/GPD+) [2] [3]

² ERA-Interim for Vienna Mapping Functions Version3 dry and wet troposphere modeling [4]

Pole Tide	ALTSDR-L1B	SGDR-E	SGDR-D	SGDR-T	SGDR Reaper v01.08	SGDR v3.1	SGDR-T	IERS Conventions 2010 [10]	IERS Conventions 2010 [10]
Radial Orbit Correction	Multi-mission cross calibration (MMXO) Version 18 [11]								

Please note: Due to missing data, no GPD/GPD+¹ [2] [3] Jason-1 Geodetic Phase is applied. Instead, VMF3² [4] is used for wet troposphere corrections.

Table 3 lists additional auxiliary parameters, which are part of the processing, but not necessarily required for SSH computation.

Table 3: Auxiliary parameters used in Baltic+ SEAL

Auxiliary parameter	Reference
Distance to coast based on SEAVOX v16 coastlines ³	SEAVOX version 16 [12]
Land-Water mask	Global Self-consistent, Hierarchical, High-resolution Geography Database (GSHHG) [13]
External open water classification based on sea-ice concentration	Sea ice concentrations from Nimbus-7 SMMR and DMSP SSM/I-SSMIS Passive Microwave Data, Version 1 [14]
Sea-ice charts including different Ice-types	Sea-ice charts provided by Finnish Meteorological Institute [15]

GPD/GPD+ wet troposphere correction

One requirement of Baltic+ SEAL is the use of the GPD/GPD+¹ [2] [3] wet troposphere correction, if the correction is fully available during the mission period. However, in case of entirely or partly missing data VMF3² [4] data is used. Following figure shows exemplary the differences between both datasets.

³ Marineregions.org Baltic Sea <http://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=23619>

Figure 2: Top row, Jason-2 (Cycle 108, Pass 111) and bottom row, Envisat (Cycle 41, Pass 502) along-track comparison of GPD+/GPD (blue) vs. VMF3 (red) wet tropospheric correction. Maps indicate GPD+/GPD along-track correction.

Additional Ocean Tide Models

Tides are generally small, with an amplitude of 0.1-0.2 m or less, in the Baltic Sea. However, in the western-most Kattegat area, tides are imported from the North Sea, and have an amplitude of up to about 0.5 m.

Besides FES2014 [8], three additional ocean tide models are proposed for future comparisons or analysis. Following table summarizes further included ocean tide models.

Table 4: Additional ocean tide models

Ocean Tide Model	Reference
EOT11a	Empirical Ocean Tide Model 11a [16]
GOT4.10	Goddard Ocean Tide Model 4.10 [17]
TPX08	OSU TOPEX/Poseidon Global Tidal Model 8 [18]

Figure 3 shows for one Envisat overflight the different ocean tide corrections (ocean tide and loading tide are combined). Note the small amplitudes of all models.

Figure 3: Envisat (Cycle 41, Pass 502) along-track comparison of four different ocean tide models (ocean tides and loading tides are summed). FES2014 [8] is standardly applied for SSH computations

Tide gauge data (FMI)

Abstract

The tide gauge (TG) data set contains data from tide gauges around the Baltic Sea. The main source of data is the CMEMS service and some data have been complemented from the national datasets of DMI (Denmark), FMI (Finland) and SMHI (Sweden). The spatial coverage of TGs varies around the Baltic. The eastern coast of the Baltic Proper has least coverage and the Danish Straits most (Location of TGs is shown in Fig. 4)

The TG data set will be used to validate the new altimetry datasets. Both along-track and gridded products will be evaluated. In addition, the TG dataset will be used, together with the GPS data and altimeter dataset, to evaluate the vertical land motion and the relative sea level trend.

The dataset is available from FMI in netcdf-format in unified height system (EVRF2007).

Meta-data

The dataset contains time series of sea level data from the TGs. The temporal coverage varies from few years to covering the entire period of the altimeter dataset. The temporal resolution of the data varies from 10 minutes to 1 hour. The information of temporal coverage and resolution for each TG is given country wise in Tables 5-10.

Table 5: Description of Swedish TG data collected from SMHI open data centre.

Station	Start (only since 1990 considered)	End	Time interval	Height system	Good data (%)	Bad data (%)	No QC (%)
Barseback	24/06/1992	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	34,5	0,3	65,1
BrofjordenSjov	15/05/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,6	0	1,4
Falkenberg2Sjov	25/04/2018	27/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,7	0	1,3
Forsmark	01/01/1990	27/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	32	0	68
Furuogrund	01/01/1990	28/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	34,6	0	65,4
GoteborgTorshammen	01/01/1990	28/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	32,3	0,3	67,5
Kalix-Storon	01/01/1990	29/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	51,9	0	48,1
KalmarSjov	25/04/2018	29/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	99	0,1	1
Klagshamn	01/01/1990	30/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	31,7	0	68,3
Kungsholmsfort	01/01/1990	30/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	41,1	0,1	58,8
Kungsvik	01/01/1990	31/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	31,3	0	68,7
Landsort	01/01/1990	14/09/2006	1 hour	RH2000	0	0	100
LandsortNorra	14/10/2004	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	63,4	0	36,6
MalmoHamnSjov	25/04/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,9	0,1	1
MarstrandSjov	26/05/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,8	0	1,2
Marviken	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	35,5	0	64,5
OlandsNorraudde	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	99,8	0	0,2
Onsala	24/06/2015	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	96,1	0	3,9
Oskarshamn	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	31,7	0	68,3
Oxelosund	25/04/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,7	0	1,3
Ratan	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	32,2	0	67,8
Ringhals	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	31,8	0	68,2
Simrishamn	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	32	0	68
Skagudde	01/01/1990	11/07/2018	1 hour	RH2000	33,7	0	66,3
SkaguddeSjov	04/05/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	100	0	0
Skonor	17/02/1992	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	34,1	0	65,9
Smogen	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	92,1	0	7,9
Spikarna	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	31,3	0	68,7
Stenungsund	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	99,8	0	0,2
Stockholm	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	37,5	0	62,5
Uddevalla	15/12/2010	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	16,5	0	83,5
VastervikSjov	25/04/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,7	0	1,3
Viken	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	31,6	0	68,4
VingaSjov	16/05/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,6	0,1	1,4
Visby	01/01/1990	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	32	0	68
YstadSjov	08/05/2018	26/05/2019	1 hour	RH2000	98,8	0,2	1

Table 6: Description of Finnish TG data collected from national database

Station	Start	End	Interval	Height system	Unit	Interpolated values (%)
Foglo	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,10
Hamina	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,70
Hanko	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	26,49
Helsinki	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,29
Kaskinen	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,20
Kemi	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,02
Mantyluoto	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,36
Oulu	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,99
Pietarsaari	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	1,50
Porvoo	08/04/2014	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,02
Raahe	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,41
Rauma	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,04
Turku	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	0,16
Vaasa	01/01/1990	31/12/2017	1 hour	N2000	mm	8,64

Table 7: Description of Danish TG data collected from the CMEMS service

Station	Start	End	Measurement interval	Height system	Good data (%)	Usable data (%)	Missing (%)
Aarhus	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,4	99,4	5,98
Assens	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	12,62
Bagenkop	27/11/2006	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	10,76
Ballen	15/01/1991	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,9	99,9	23,43
Bandholm	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	7,71
Bogense	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	12,29
Dragor	06/07/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	1,67
Drogden	16/03/1992	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	97,3	97,3	19,51
Faaborg	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	12,18
Fredericia	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,8	99,8	1,99
Frederikshavn	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,3	99,3	1,64
Fynshav	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,7	99,7	14,97
Gedser	26/03/1992	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	99,8	99,8	19,91
Grena	14/01/1991	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	100	100	22,29
Hesnaes	02/10/1991	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	100	100	54,82
Hobro	28/12/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	8,9
Holbaek	22/12/2011	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	100	100	2,63
Hornbaek	10/10/1991	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,8	99,8	17,56
Hov	28/12/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	2,22
Juelsminde	06/12/1996	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	23,24
Kalvehave	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,9	99,9	10,85
Karrebaeksminde	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	2,92
Kobenhavn	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,5	99,5	4,85
Koege	21/12/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,1	99,1	1,95
Korsor	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,7	99,7	2,19
NordreRose	31/08/1992	02/01/2019	varies	DVR90	99,9	99,9	43,49
Randers	28/12/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	78,8	78,8	10,04
Rodby	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,2	99,2	1,4
Rodvig	16/08/1991	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	100	100	-
Ronne	15/02/1994	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	99,6	99,6	-
Roskilde	21/12/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	2,53
SjaellandsOdde	09/12/1991	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	100	100	-
Skagen	04/12/1991	04/03/2019	varies	DVR90	100	100	-
Slipshavn	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99	99	2,12
Sonderborg	01/01/2014	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	7,69
Spodsbjerg	19/01/1991	21/12/2005	varies	DVR90	100	100	-
Tejn	01/01/2005	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	99,8	99,8	4,19
Udbyhoej	03/01/2012	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	1,96
Vedbaek	21/12/2011	04/03/2019	10 min	DVR90	100	100	9,51

Table 8: Description of Estonian TG data collected from the CMEMS service

Station	Start	End	Measurement interval	Height system	Good (%)	Usable (%)	Missing (%)
Eisma	07/02/2017	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,6	100	0,2
Heltermaa	01/01/2017	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	10,1
Kelnase	07/02/2017	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,1	99,5	0,22
Kuivastu	23/03/2010	18/12/2015	1 hour	BHS77	99,4	99,4	2,9
Lehtma	23/10/2006	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	7,44
Leppneeme	07/02/2017	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	0,22
Munalaid	03/02/2016	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,9	99,9	7,71
Paldiski	23/10/2006	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	7,39
Parnu	22/10/2004	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	75,4	75,4	8,95
Rohukula	30/11/2009	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,6	99,6	13,31
Sillamae	23/10/2006	12/05/2016	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	4,01
Soru	14/11/2005	04/12/2015	1 hour	BHS77	99,7	99,7	26,83
Tallinnamadal	12/01/2012	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	79,8	79,8	3,61
Tallinn	14/11/2005	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,9	99,9	4,86
Triigi	23/03/2010	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,8	99,8	39,74
Vahemadal	23/02/2015	04/07/2018	1 hour	BHS77	81,2	81,2	6,85
Virtsu	01/12/2009	04/03/2019	1 hour	BHS77	99,8	99,8	10,32

Table 9: Description of German TG data collected from the CMEMS service

Station	Start	End	Measurement interval	Height system	Good (%)	Usable (%)	Missing (%)
Althagen	03/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	99,9	99,9	14,06
Barhoeft	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	99,8	99,8	2,15
Greifswald	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	100	100	2,57
Koserow	20/11/2005	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	98,7	98,7	5,30
Rostock	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	99,9	99,9	1,29
Sassnitz	24/01/2005	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	99,9	99,9	6,31
Stralsund	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	100	100	1,94
TimmendorfPoel	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	100	100	3,07
Ueckermuende	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	100	100	2,29
Warnemuende	25/01/2005	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	100	100	3,18
Wismar	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	99,8	99,8	2,04
WittowerFahre	27/01/2011	27/08/2012	1 hour	SNN76	100	100	2.13
Wolgast	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	SNN76	99,9	99,9	2,08
Eckernfoerde	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	3,62
Flensburg	26/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	7,02
Heiligenhafen	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	2,52
Kappeln	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	4,26
KielHoltenau	24/01/2005	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	99,4	99,4	4,64
KielLT	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	3,13
Langballigau	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	9,31
Luebeck	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	1,9
Neustadt	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	2,54
Schleimuende	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	89,8	89,8	11,1
Schleswig	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	5,99
Travemuende	24/01/2005	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	3,94
Kalkgrund	27/01/2011	04/03/2019	15 min	DHHN92	100	100	8,22

Table 10: Description of Latvian, Lithuanian, Polish and Russian TG data collected from the CMEMS service

Station	Start	End	Measurement interval	Height system	Good (%)	Usable (%)	Missing (%)
Latvia							
Daugavgriva	27/01/2005	29/05/2018	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	9,3
Kolka	27/01/2005	29/05/2018	1 hour	BHS77	100	100	9,98
Lithuania							
Klaipeda	07/02/2006	31/08/2014	1 hour	BHS77	99,3	99,3	25,13
Poland							
Hel	09/02/2006	08/08/2007	10 min	BHS77	100	100	51,58
Russia							
Hogland	29/04/2010	18/04/2018	3 hour	BHS77	98,4	98,4	29,56
Kronstadt	20/10/2005	04/03/2019	varies	BHS77	99,8	99,8	-
StPetersburg	21/07/2004	04/03/2019	varies	BHS77	99,9	99,9	-

Data description

The TGs are not evenly placed around the Baltic Sea. There is quite high coverage in the Danish Straits, but only few stations in the eastern coast of the Baltic Proper. The locations of the Tide gauges are presented for the whole Baltic Sea in Fig. 4 and for different sub-basins in Figs. 5-11.

The quality of the TG data is presented as given in the national databases or in the CMEMS dataset. Amount of good quality data, to be used in the validation, has been evaluated and is presented for each TG in Tables 5-10.

In the conversion of the height system from the national system to the EVRF2007, station specific coefficients have been used for Finnish and Swedish TGs. For other TGs country wise coefficients have been used according to data provided by the German Federal Agency of Cartography and Geodesy (<https://evrs.bkg.bund.de/Subsites/EVRS/EN/Projects/HeightDatumRel/height-datum-rel.html>).

Figure 4: All tide gauge stations available via CMEMS. **Note** that the stations are colour coded by country, except for Latvia, Lithuania and Poland that are indicated by the same colour (purple).

Figure 5: Location of TG's in the Gulf of Finland

Figure 6: Location of TG's in the Bothnian Bay

Figure 7: Location of TG's in the Bothnian Sea

Figure 8: Location of TG's in the Baltic Proper

Figure 9: Location of TG's in the Arkona and Bornholm basins

Figure 10: Location of TG's in the Belt Sea

Figure 11: Location of TG's in the Kattegat and the Sound

GPS data (FMI)

Abstract

The GPS data set includes official station velocities from the Class A stations collected from the EUREF Permanent GNSS Network. GPS data will be used in the WP3.7, where combination of altimetry, TGs and GPS data is used for analysis of vertical land motion analysis and derivation of relative sea level trend

Meta-data

The dataset covers the GPS data from Class A stations collected from the GNSS Network (<http://epncb.oma.be/>). The dataset includes official station velocities from each station. Data is available from FMI.

Data description

The available GPS stations from GNSS Network for the Baltic Sea area are shown in Fig. 12. Only some of the stations are in the vicinity of the TGs and therefore usable in the analysis of the vertical land motion and the relative sea level trend.

Vertical velocities from the Class A GPS stations has been collected and the distance of each station to the nearest TG has been calculated. Examples of GPS stations within 30 km from TGs are shown in Fig 13.

Figure 12: Location of the GPS stations (red x) and TG stations (purple dots) in the Baltic Sea

Distance between TG and GPS ≤ 30 km

Figure

13: Location of the GPS stations (red x) with 30 km radius from the TG stations (purple dots) in the Baltic Sea

Model data (DMI)

Abstract

Hydrodynamic model data will be used for the gridded high-temporal (1-3 days) resolution data set (WP4.2). It is referenced to the mean sea surface, and was extracted from the DMI DKSS operational storm surge model, which is

used for the storm surge warning at DMI and has a proven performance in the Baltic Sea including Kattegat (see <http://ocean.dmi.dk/validations/surges/index.uk.php>).

The statistical sea level variability product from the EMODNET Baltic Sea Checkpoint project will be used for comparison with the monthly gridded sea level product [19]

A blended altimetry-TG product from the ESA DUE eSurge project will be used for intercomparison with the high temporal resolution gridded dataset where applicable [20].

Meta-data

The DMI DKSS model setup used here is the operational setup used at DMI for storm surge modelling and warning⁴. The DKSS setup consists of five model domains (Fig. 14 and table 11):

- **NOAMOD** - 2-dimensional mesocale model that calculates sea level as a function of wind speed and air pressure. Generates boundary data (external surge) for the regional 3-dimensionan model
- **North Sea - Baltic Sea** - 3-dimensional regional model with subdomains
- **Transition Area** - high resolution model of the waters south of Skagen and west of Bornholm
- **Wadden Sea** - high resolution model of the German Bight
- **Limfjord** - high resolution fjord (appended) model

For this project, data from the North Sea - Baltic Sea domain and the Transition Area domain will be used. In 2019, a further model domain of Roskilde Fjord and Isefjord in Denmark (not shown) has been included in DMI DKSS, but will not be used for this project.

⁴ For more info, see <http://ocean.dmi.dk/models/hbm.uk.php>

Figure 14: The five domains in the DKSS setup: NOAMOD (blue), North Sea - Baltic Sea (red), Transition area (red), Wadden Sea (red) and Limfjord (light blue).

Table 11: Model setup and subdomains.

Model	NOAMOD	HBM North Sea - Baltic Sea	HBM Transition Area	HBM Wadden Sea	HBM Limfjord
Spatial resolution	6' lat 10' lon (6 n.m.)	3' lat 5' lon (3 n.m.)	30" lat 50" lon (0.5 n.m.)	1' lat 1'24" lon (1 n.m.)	12" lat 20" lon (0.2 n.m.)
Vertical layers	1	50	52	24	9
Max. top layer thickness	900m	8m	2m	8m	2m
Time step: Barotropic: Baroclinic: Ice	15s - -	30s 90s 900s	15s 90s 900s	30s 90s 900s	10s 20s 900s
Atm. forcing	ECMWF GLM	Harmonie NEA ECMWF GLM	Harmonie NEA ECMWF GLM	Harmonie NEA ECMWF GLM	Harmonie NEA ECMWF GLM

Area: longitude	21W-13E	4W-30E	9E-15E	6E-10E	8E-10E
Area: latitude	48N-66N	Baltic Sea: 48N-66N North Sea: 48N-59N	53N-57½N	53N-56N	57N-58N
Open boundaries	Radiation condition	Surge contribution from NOAMOD, tidal wave (17 constituents), monthly climatology fields for T and S via a sponge layer	nested in regional model	nested in regional model	boundary data from regional and transition area model

Data description

The DMI DKSS model data is deviation from Sea Level Mean (DSL_M). Data is saved in monthly netcdf files, with hourly resolution. The spatial resolution of the output is 3 nautical miles (nm). The data covers year 2017. Figure 15 shows an example of the model output: the DSL_M for January 5th at 00:00, during a storm surge event in the Western Baltic.

Figure 15: Deviation from Sea Level Mean on January 5th 00:00 2017.

SAR and optical data (TUM)

Abstract

The results of the open water detection within the sea-ice layer based on an unsupervised classification strategy are validated by a comparison with external optical and radar (SAR) images. The images are spatial and temporal collocated with respect to the altimetry overflight locations and times. In order to minimize effects of different

observation scenarios, for example caused by the sea-ice drift, acquisition gaps between the validation data and altimetry observations may not exceed one hour. Furthermore, in case of optical validation data a maximum cloud coverage of 44% is allowed to maximize the potential for a reliable comparison.

The validation datasets are obtained from different remote sensing missions and data centres, which are introduced in the following parts.

Meta-data

The validation data covers mainly the Bay of Bothnia (northern part of the Baltic Sea), due to the seasonal sea-ice coverage. However, in case of the optical datasets the data availability is dependent on the illumination and cloud conditions during the winter months. Table 12 lists all used optical and SAR validation data sources and specifications.

Table 12: Optical (light-brown) and SAR (light-green) datasets and characteristics used in Baltic SEAL

Mission (agency)	Sensor	Pixel Size (m)	Product Level/ID	Data centre / Data hub
Sentinel-2A/B (ESA/Copernicus)	MSI (Multi-Spectral Imager)	10 – 30	Level-2A S2MSI2A/B	Copernicus Open Access Hub ⁵
Landsat – 5 (NASA/USGS)	TM (Thematic Mapper)	30	Level-1 precision and terrain corrected product (L1TP)	U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer ⁶
Landsat – 7 (NASA/USGS)	ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus)	30	Level-1 precision and terrain corrected product (L1TP)	U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer ⁵
Landsat – 8 (NASA/USGS)	OLI (Operational Land Imager)	30	Level-1 precision and terrain corrected product (L1TP)	U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer ⁵
Sentinel-1A/B (ESA/Copernicus)	Sentinel-1 C-SAR	40	Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) Extra-Wide (EW)	Alaska Satellite Facility (ASF) DAAC processed by ESA ⁷

Data description

The different validation datasets are processed to enable a good discrimination between open ocean and sea-ice areas. In case of the optical datasets spectral bands are selected, which provide good contrast between the various surface conditions. The composites are dependent on the sensor characteristics and band availability:

- Landsat-5: 4,3,2 (0.76-0.90, 0.63-0.69, 0.52-0.60) μm
- Landsat-7: 4,3,2 (0.76-0.90, 0.63-0.69, 0.52-0.60) μm
- Landsat-8: 5,4,3 (0.85-0.88, 0.64-0.67, 0.53-0.59) μm
- Sentinel-2A/B: 8,4,3 (0.84, 0.67, 0.56) μm

⁵ Copernicus Open Access Hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home>)

⁶ USGS Earth Explorer (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>)

⁷ Alaska Satellite Facility Distributed Active Archive Center (<https://search.asf.alaska.edu/#/?flightDirs=>)

In case of Sentinel-2A/B the images are down-scaled to 30m pixel resolution in order to provide consistency with the Landsat mission. The radar missions provide C-band dual-polarized (Sentinel-1A/B) snapshots.

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